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Publish your undergraduate research!
A mandatory course for master students in engineering

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Conference Key Areas: How Learning Spaces Support Innovative T&L, Innovative Teaching and Learning Methods, Philosophy and Purpose of Engineering Education

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INTRODUCTION

During the curriculum redesign of a master course in engineering, it was decided to enhance the ability of students ...

- ... to express themselves effectively,
- ... to gain confidence in their research activities,
- ... to argue, reason and discuss scientifically,
- ... to evaluate the work of others and
- ... to align with scientific standards and engineering conventions.

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In short, a course was created with a simple assignment: Publish your research! In the following, we will relate our course model to existing approaches, set a perspective on undergraduate research and evaluate course results.

1 BACKGROUND AND EXISTING APPROACHES

With the completion of their bachelor thesis, engineering students have usually carried out and compiled a genuine piece of research. However, even with a thorough supervision, the exposition of results and arguments often remains limited to a small internal circle of stakeholders in a protected research environment and/or in an examination process. The students therefore miss the learning experience of being challenged by a broader audience of experts and peers. Such an advance into new and open terrain may look like trouble ahead but is often the doorstep to new advances in learning. This is well described by Meyer and Land [1] with the threshold concept of learning, which can ultimately “lead not only to transformed thought but to a transfiguration of identity and adoption of an extended discourse”. This transformation can be stimulated by the creation of liminal spaces. Walkington et al. [2] have shown that undergraduate research conferences are favourable opportunities to open such spaces, helping students to “reformulate their taken-for-granted frames of meaning by engaging in critical reflection, through a process of dialogue with others. Such dialogue is a central element of transactional communication.” Undergraduate research conferences like the National Conference on Undergraduate Research (NCUR) in the USA exist for a long time and have spawned successful offspring in other countries. They provide a suitable space for students to take a step beyond their classroom barrier, offer a guided (review) process towards high-quality scientific communication adhering to engineering standards and thus allow them grow confidence in their ability to sustain among peers.

At an institutional level, various approaches to learn and train the written and oral presentation of scientific work can be found. Commonly, the required skills of students are developed throughout continuous assignments to write lab reports, project documentations and, finally, the bachelor thesis. Ideally, the student develops her/his own style and skills with respect to authorship by learning from various staff members, but the learning process is rarely made explicit or guided. On the contrary, ambitious and valuable courses like “Writing your thesis” or “Presentations for engineers” exist, but are often offered on a voluntary basis and/or outside the faculty, see e.g. [3]. This can convey misleading messages with respect to developing a self-confident authorship. It implies that communication and presentation is only an add-on for either those with special weaknesses or special interests and may thus remain detached from the development of the student’s identity as an engineer.

Within computer science education, an integrated approach has been proposed by several researchers in the form of mini-conferences as a course model. This has been successfully applied in the past to both undergraduate and graduate courses [4, 5]. With our approach, we apply a similar model to a master course in engineering, assuming that almost none of the participants have published the research conducted

for their bachelor theses. In contrast to the courses described and referenced in [4] and [5], our students have already completed the research work that provides the necessary basis for paper writing and exercising communication and presentation skills [6, 7].

2 IDEA AND GOALS

For the development of our own approach [6], we argue that the emergence of scientific communication skills should not only be an explicit and integral part of the curriculum but must be developed as a competence from within the faculty. To achieve this, we expose all our master students to the basic standards of peer-reviewed research and provide the opportunity to present their own work on a conference-like level. For this, every master student has to take her/his bachelor thesis as a starting point and expose it to a full conference publication schedule during one semester. We therefore simulate an engineering conference which requires the student to actively prepare, revise and present her/his paper and a poster (see Fig. 1). Thus the publication process becomes a project with the student/author as the manager of her/his success, placing the responsibility for the associated learning experience into the hand of the student. Along the publication process, the students find out about current research in their discipline and become engaged in research discussions. According to Healy and Jenkins [8], this approach can be classified as research-led and research-tutored, as the research project itself, i.e. the thesis, has been completed before the course.

3 COURSE CONCEPT AND CONTENT

The course “Engineering Conferences” was developed for the curriculum of a master course within a medium-sized faculty of mechanical and process engineering (approx. 1500 students) of a medium-sized University of Applied Sciences in Germany. The course is mandatory and 6 credits according to the ECTS-scheme can be earned. The established language of scientific communication, English, is used as a means of instruction (EMI) throughout the full course, which is open to approx. 30 students and

Figure 1. Reducing page numbers by two orders of magnitude: Evolution of key findings and the core message from thesis to paper to poster

can be booked every term. The underlying concept is a simulated engineering conference, with special emphasis on the upfront publication schedule including a full review process that employs the course participants as peers.

The detailed course outline is presented in Table 1. Special care was directed at the design of group work exercises: Students develop content and gain learning experience, with the lecturer standing aside serving as moderator (see exercises in bold face of column 3 in Table 1). As an example for these active learning exercise, the course starts with an “elevator talk” [9]: Each student has to explain the topic of her/his bachelor thesis to other students within two minutes. For most of them, it is the first time talking about their thesis topic in English in a very limited period of time and with the aim to convey a message. This deliberate push beyond the student’s comfort zone is turned into confidence by one or two repetitions.

To model the paper submission and review process, the free web-based conference management system EasyChair is used, which allows to set deadlines, upload papers, define roles such as authors, reviewers and chairs, organize reviews etc. This is not only easy to use for teachers and students but also a real conference standard. After

Table 1. Course Outline: Tasks and Exercises

Unit	Tasks	Exercise (bold face: group work)	Schedule
1	Orientation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The shape of science How to find a scientific paper 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> identify own field of work identify position on science map find example paper 	Week 1
2	Comprehension: Reading, understanding and evaluating a scientific paper	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Elevator talk”: my thesis is about ... study example paper conduct a simple review present findings to group 	Week 2
3	State-of-the-art survey: Finding related work and peers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> identify important work of others understand and relate to own work 	Week 3-4
4	Paper compilation: Developing a thread and structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> identify core results and/or message collect and arrange headlines, graphs and main arguments 	Week 5
5	Paper layout / references: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Referencing and reference styles Organizing a bibliography and referencing tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> use example tool for finding, editing, and archiving references apply reference style to example sources 	Week 6
6	Paper layout / style: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Editing and publishing tools Paper style guide and template 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> learn and test the capabilities of publishing tools get familiar with paper style guide 	Week 7-8
Exam element: paper submitted (Week 8)			
7	Peer-review: Quality control and improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> identify elements, stakeholder, effects and defects of review processes peer-papers of other authors in class 	Week 9
Exam element: two reviews conducted (Week 10)			
8	Poster presentation: Designing a scientific poster	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> arrange information and layout evaluate story and effect 	Week 10-14
Exam element: poster presentation day (public, Week 15)			

the paper submission, students are requested to conduct two blind reviews of papers submitted by their peers in class. This includes filling out a review form, which requires to state a reason for each rating and also the upload of the reviewed paper with the reviewer's annotations. If nothing else, the latter is an important and visual verification of the engagement of the reviewer with the papers. In real life, reviewers are volunteers, highly motivated, and usually concerned about their scientific reputation. This intrinsic motivation cannot be expected from all our students but at least some extrinsic motivation is installed, since the course rating is partly dependent on the quality of the reviews.

The last part of the course is dedicated to the preparation of the poster. The poster presentation day is the final event of the course and takes place in the main entrance hall of the faculty building (see Figure 2). While each student has to deliver a two-minute keynote on her/his research topic, the others are free to browse the final product of their peers or to answer questions of visiting faculty members and students. Both poster and keynote are assessed by the lecturers on the spot resulting in the final grade for the course.

Credits for the course are earned for the poster presentation (counts 60%) and the paper including two peer reviews (40%).

4 EXPERIENCE AND REFLECTION

Until now, we have organized and applied the conference concept in the form of a paper submission and poster presentation four times in successive semesters. Over a hundred participants in the mandatory course achieved an average course results of 91%. According to the anonymous self-assessment of the students, evaluated summer 2017, at least 70% of the participants noticed the improvement of their communication skills which can be seen as a success with regards to the goals set in the introduction and section 2. The review process and subsequent evaluation by the lecturers shows a high quality of the submitted papers. The goal to publish research according to international conference standards is met by about 50% of the submitted papers in the course.

Figure 2. Poster presentation day

Figure 3. Evaluation of learning goals

The implementation of the course “Engineering Conferences” has led to a significant increase of activity among both faculty staff and students in social networks for researchers and scientists such as ResearchGate, thus increasing the visibility of research of our university. This effect is boosted by the final event of the poster presentations which vividly enhances scientific and informal exchange within the home faculty and its neighbouring faculty. The poster presentation is now an established bi-annual public event and it stands as one of the rare events in the curriculum where the result of learning is proudly made visible outside the classroom. In the course evaluation, students are very positive about this culminating event. They express personal satisfaction based on their success in delivering their research, which indicates that some of the engagement for a real conference can be captured.

However, the real conference remains the ultimate experience: Voluntary participation and a rigorous selection process are key drivers to self-motivation and “one-off” experience. Due to the course, we see a steep increase of interest among students to pursue their own research project with a focus to publish. With a local sponsorship of the Association of German Engineers (VDI) we are able to reward three conference participations per year for the best papers from the course. It has to be noted that not all students are happy with the effort required to master the course, especially those who are not interested in a research career. Despite the expressed improvement in effectiveness and precision with respect to communication in the engineering profession (see Fig. 3) the students do not yet realize this as a gain for a career in industry.

For the course preparation as well as during course delivery we make extensive use of the vast resources available on scientific writing practices and research communication. Here, we highlight two sources that have already appeared to be useful to a large community: Firstly, the survival guide on paper writing by Holst [10], salted with worldly-wise glimpses behind the scene and peppered with sketches by Jorge Cham, the maker of PhDcomics.com. Secondly, the compilation of the reference style required by the American Psychological Association (APA), provided by the University of Queensland Library [11]. It provides a precise answer, including examples, to the question of how to cite virtually anything. The following keywords are suitable to find more useful resources related to scientific publishing; they are loosely arranged in the order of increased caution required when employed in class: DOI.org, IMRaD-Style, JabRef, Shape of Science, ResearchGate, PhDcomics, SciGen, SciHub.

Eventually, we found ourselves doing research in teaching methods and scientific communication, resulting in a recursive learning – research – teaching experience. Since the course “Engineering Conferences” was our first genuine team teaching experience, we ourselves had entered liminal space and considerably stimulated our life-long learning adventure. How did this work out for our students?

From the beginning the students are pushed out into the open and exposed to active learning experiences such as group activity and, overall, to master their publication

process as their own project. This became especially apparent, when students were challenged to express their rationale, e.g. in outlining the main theme or thread of their work. A gain in literacy and thus confidence in their own work was observed from one lesson to the next whenever the student was willing to engage with her/his research. Many students openly expressed that genuine research on the work of others in the field was a first-time experience for them as a result of the course, and that they wished to have known about these findings during their thesis. We thus witnessed at various occasions that troublesome knowledge led to transformed thought and dialogue acted as a central element of transactional communication [2]. Such “magic moments” are likely to occur by opening liminal spaces, which small active learning elements can provide as well as the overall exposure to a conference situation.

5 SUMMARY

A master course module was designed, implemented, and tested with the goal to improve scientific communication skills of engineering students. As the name “Engineering Conferences” suggests, training is based around a mock-up conference, where students have to present the results of their bachelor thesis in a paper and as a poster. The combination of the following features distinguishes the course concept from similar approaches:

1. It has a storyline (conference participation) with a public finish (poster presentation day).
2. It engages undergraduate students as researchers and it turns the publication of their bachelor thesis into a project.
3. It is mandatory for all master students of the engineering faculty.
4. It is delivered by teachers/researchers from within the faculty, i.e. from “engineering native speakers”.
5. It can easily be copied and integrated into any STEM curriculum.

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